

Eukaryotes + NCLDVs + some bacteria

Prokaryotes

Trichomonas vaginalis

Prokaryotes

Tritrichomonas foetus

Prokaryotes

Giardia intestinalis
Trepomonas sp. PC1
Giardia muris

Prokaryotes

Carpediemonas membranifera
Carpediemonas frisla

Prokaryotes

